

SCM-Arena: A Behavioral Benchmark for LLM Decision-Making in Supply Chains

Abhianv "Sunny" Hasija
Grand Valley State University
hasijaa@gvsu.edu

Vincent E. Castillo
The Ohio State University
castillo.230@osu.edu

April 2026

Abstract

SCM-Arena defines a reproducible behavioral evaluation protocol for LLM decision policies in delayed-feedback supply chain systems. Version 1 is frozen as of January 31, 2026 and comprises 75 models, 144 conditions per model, 5 replications per condition, and over 53,000 total episodes. Unlike knowledge-based benchmarks that test isolated question-answering, SCM-Arena places models in the role of ordering agents across a four-tier supply chain simulation derived from the Beer Game with varying demand patterns, information visibility, decision memory, and prompt framing conditions. Performance is assessed through cost ratio relative to a human baseline, demand amplification (bullwhip effect), and behavioral descriptors of ordering coordination and decision complexity. Aggregated results are publicly accessible at scm-arena.com. This paper describes the protocol design, metrics, and platform.

1 Introduction

LLMs are increasingly being used for operational decisions, but the tools for evaluating whether they belong in those roles have not kept up. Existing benchmarks test factual recall, reasoning on isolated problems, or in most cases, performance on static tasks with a single correct answer. These benchmarks fail to capture what happens when a model's decisions interact with a dynamic system over time, where mistakes compound, information is delayed and coordination across agents determines outcomes.

Supply chain management makes this gap even more evident. Ordering decisions in a multi-tier supply chain are not made in isolation: one tier's order becomes another tier's demand signal. Information delays and partial visibility are structural features of the environment, and not just edge cases to be accounted for. Small behavioral differences in models, repeated over tasks, can produce large downstream effects like the bullwhip effect, in which demand variability amplifies as it propagates upstream through the chain.

Thus, evaluating LLMs for operational deployment requires behavioral benchmarks that measure how a model acts over time inside a system with feedback loops. SCM-Arena places models in a well studied supply chain simulation, while varying conditions systematically, and measures behavior across repeated episodes. The output is a behavioral profile covering performance under normal conditions, degradation when information and memory are restricted, and failure regimes under demand stress.

To our knowledge, SCM-Arena is the first benchmark designed for repeated behavioral evaluation of LLM decision-making in a dynamic supply chain setting.

2 The Beer Game as a Benchmark Environment

The Beer Game is a multi-tier supply chain simulation developed at MIT and used in operations management for decades to study coordination failure, information delays, and the bullwhip effect [1]. It traditionally models a four-tier supply chain (retailer, wholesaler, distributor, factory) in which each tier independently makes ordering decisions based on limited information. Orders take time to arrive, and inventory and backlog accumulate based on the mismatch between supply and demand. The game is widely used in both research and management education because its structure reliably produces coordination failures even among experienced players.

The Beer Game has several properties that make it suitable as a benchmark environment for LLM decision-making. It is well-characterized: human baselines, failure modes, and the dynamics of the bullwhip effect are extensively documented [1, 2]. It is also structurally constrained: the environment has defined state variables, decision points, and outcome metrics, which enables systematic experimental manipulation. Moreover, it is ecologically relevant: the coordination problems it encodes, partial information, feedback delays, role-differentiated decisions, are representative of real operational settings.

SCM-Arena uses variants of the Beer Game as its simulation environment. Large Language Models (LLMs) act as ordering agents at each tier, receiving state information as specified by the experimental condition and producing integer order quantities at each round.

3 Benchmark Design

SCM-Arena evaluates each model across a fully crossed experimental design defined by five factors:

Scenario (S) controls the demand pattern seen by the retailer tier: *classic* (steady demand, the Beer Game baseline), *random* (stochastic demand varying each round), *shock* (a one-time demand jump testing recovery), and *seasonal* (periodic demand swings testing tracking).

Visibility (V) controls what information each tier receives: *local* (own state only), *adjacent* (own state plus neighboring tier information), and *full* (end-to-end chain visibility).

Memory (M) controls the decision history available to the model: *none* (myopic, no prior rounds), *short* (a limited history window), and *full* (complete run history or summary).

Prompt framing (P) distinguishes *neutral* prompts (minimal guidance) from *specific* prompts (structured objectives and constraints).

Game mode (G) distinguishes the classic Beer Game rules from a modern variant used in SCM-Arena.

The condition space is defined formally as:

$$\begin{aligned}
 S &\in \{\text{classic, random, shock, seasonal}\} \\
 V &\in \{\text{local, adjacent, full}\} \\
 M &\in \{\text{none, short, full}\} \\
 P &\in \{\text{neutral, specific}\} \\
 G &\in \{\text{classic, modern}\} \\
 \mathcal{C} &= S \times V \times M \times P \times G, \quad |\mathcal{C}| = 144
 \end{aligned}$$

Each model m is evaluated over all $c \in \mathcal{C}$ with $R = 5$ replications and $T = 52$ rounds per episode.

Across 75 models, this specification yields 10,800 model-condition cells and over 53,000 total episodes. The platform uses fully deterministic seeding to ensure full reproducibility. The models are sampled theoretically: spanning open-weight and proprietary families, with parameter counts scaling from sub 1 billion to frontier-scale (ChatGPT, Claude, etc.)

4 Metrics

SCM-Arena reports two outcome metrics and two behavioral descriptors.

Cost ratio is the primary outcome measure. It compares total system cost, summing inventory holding and backlog costs across all tiers and rounds, to the Sterman human reference baseline [1]. A value of 1.0 matches the human baseline; values above 1 indicate higher cost. Cost ratio above 10 indicates likely coordination failure; above 100 indicates severe breakdown. Large values under stress conditions reflect runaway ordering or persistent backlog and are read as system-level signals rather than noise.

Bullwhip measures demand amplification across the supply chain. It is the ratio of order variance to demand variance, with higher values indicating greater instability as demand signals propagate upstream. Bullwhip above 3 indicates elevated instability; above 10 indicates an unstable regime.

Entropy is a normalized Shannon entropy ($H \in [0, 1]$) computed over the distribution of ordering decisions across tiers. Low entropy means tiers order similarly (tight coordination); high entropy means dispersed, fragmented ordering. Entropy describes behavioral structure, not outcome quality.

Complexity is a standardized score (approximately -1 to 1) measuring the information-intensity of a model’s decision behavior relative to all models in the benchmark. Negative values indicate simpler, more rigid responses; positive values indicate richer, more adaptive behavior. Zero is the benchmark median.

Cost ratio and bullwhip describe outcomes; entropy and complexity describe how those outcomes are produced. Two models can achieve similar cost ratios through very different behavioral mechanisms, and the descriptors are designed to distinguish them.

5 Results and Benchmark Interpretation

5.1 Aggregate Performance

Across 75 models and 53,989 valid episodes, no model achieved a cost ratio below 10, meaning no model matched or beat the Sterman human baseline under the full condition set. The median cost

ratio across models is 72.5. Twenty-five models (33%) remain below 50; thirty models (40%) exceed 100, indicating likely coordination failure; nine models (12%) exceed 1,000, indicating severe system breakdown.

The five lowest aggregate cost ratios are: kimi-k2-thinking (18.6), deepseek-v3.2 (19.3), qwen3:4b (19.6), olmo2:7b (20.3), and gemma2:2b (20.8). Several frontier-scale models appear near the top of this ranking, but gemma2:2b, a 2-billion parameter model, also places in the top five. This illustrates why aggregate cost ratio alone is an unreliable indicator of genuine supply chain competence.

5.2 The Passive-Strategy Problem: gemma2:2b as a Case Study

gemma2:2b orders exactly 4 units in 48.9% of its 149,760 agent-round decisions. The initial steady-state demand in the Beer Game is 4 units per round. The model is not adapting to supply chain dynamics; it is repeating the baseline value.

This strategy performs well under the classic game parameterization precisely because 4 is the approximately correct answer. In classic game mode, gemma2:2b achieves cost ratios of 0.6, 1.7, 2.9, and 4.2 on the classic, shock, seasonal, and random demand scenarios respectively, figures that appear to indicate exceptional performance. Switching to the modern game parameterization, where the steady-state target shifts, the same model falls to cost ratios of 33-39 across all scenarios, indistinguishable from middling performers.

The behavioral descriptors surface this directly. gemma2:2b has the 5th lowest complexity score in the benchmark (-0.445) and an entropy of 0.693, both indicating a narrow, near-constant decision distribution. Its aggregate cost ratio of 20.8 is an artifact of parameter alignment between a near-constant ordering policy and the classic game’s baseline demand level, not a signal of adaptive competence.

By contrast, kimi-k2-thinking achieves an aggregate cost ratio of 18.6 with a complexity score of -0.054 and entropy of 0.838. Its scenario profile in classic game mode is more uniform: 8.3 (classic), 9.7 (random), 12.3 (shock), and 6.1 (seasonal). The performance gap between the two models in the classic scenario is large (0.6 vs. 8.3), but that gap reverses the interpretation: gemma2:2b’s low classic-scenario score reflects lucky alignment between a degenerate strategy and a specific parameterization, while kimi-k2-thinking’s consistency across scenarios reflects a more robust behavioral policy.

The gemma2:2b case is what the multi-metric design is for. Cost ratio and bullwhip describe outcomes; complexity and entropy describe the behavioral mechanism producing those outcomes. A model with low cost ratio and low complexity warrants scrutiny: it may be exploiting structural regularities in one parameterization rather than demonstrating generalizable ordering competence. The condition sensitivity plots on the platform expose this kind of performance fragility. A model whose cost ratio degrades sharply from classic to modern game mode, or from full to local visibility, is flagging a narrow behavioral repertoire regardless of its aggregate rank.

5.3 Condition Sensitivity

Across all models, the median effect of restricting visibility from full to local is modest: median cost ratio increases from 33.2 to 34.9. The median effect of restricting memory is larger and directionally counterintuitive: short memory produces the lowest median cost ratio (31.7), full memory the highest (36.7), and no memory falls between (33.2).

A natural candidate explanation is context window truncation: if full-memory prompts exceed model context limits, the model may receive silently truncated histories that are worse than no history at all. We checked prompt lengths directly. At round 52 under full memory and full visibility, the worst-case condition, maximum prompt lengths range from approximately 930 to 1,090 tokens across all 75 models. The Ollama default context window is 2,048 tokens; no model in the benchmark approaches its limit.

However, context window limits do not appear to be the cause. Full-memory prompts supply models with a complete record of prior decisions, including any panic-ordering phase that occurred in earlier rounds. In runs that entered a bullwhip spiral, the round-52 prompt contains 51 abbreviated history entries documenting escalating upstream orders, in some cases reaching order quantities of 600, 800, or 1,200 units before the system nominally stabilized. A model reading this history at round 52 is presented with a trajectory of failure as its decision context, even when current inventory and backlog figures indicate the system has since corrected. Short memory, by providing only the most recent three rounds, effectively filters out this failure record and anchors the model to the current state. No memory provides only the present state with no historical reference at all.

This suggests that LLMs in sequential supply chain tasks can be harmed by their own behavioral history, that the damage caused in early rounds persists as a context signal that distorts later decisions. The pattern is itself a manifestation of the bullwhip dynamic: the failure record persists as a context signal even after the physical system corrects.

6 The SCM-Arena Platform and Reproducibility

SCM-Arena v1 is publicly accessible at scm-arena.com. Users can browse all 75 models, filtering by family, scenario, visibility, memory, and prompt type. A comparison tool places 2 to 4 models side by side with aligned sensitivity plots that show how cost ratio and bullwhip shift as conditions are restricted. Each model page provides full condition-level data, degradation curves, and 95% bootstrap confidence intervals on aggregate cost ratio.

The benchmark is frozen as of January 31, 2026. Seeds, configuration hashes, and run artifacts are versioned internally. The platform serves pre-computed static JSON from the analysis pipeline and does not recompute metrics at runtime. Aggregated results are publicly accessible, though raw episode data is not released.

The platform is intended to support comparison across models and not ranking. No single model dominates across all conditions, and the benchmark does not try to identify one. It supports two forms of analysis. Within-model sensitivity analysis tracks how a given model’s behavior changes as conditions tighten. Across-model comparison identifies which models degrade more gracefully under constraint. The question both forms address together is whether a model in a particular operating environment can act autonomously, needs human oversight, or should be replaced by a rule-based fallback.

7 Relation to Prior Work

Prior work applying LLMs to supply chain settings has largely focused on knowledge retrieval, optimization support, and agent-based frameworks for specific tasks [3, 4]. Most directly related is recent work applying LLMs to the Beer Game in a RAG-augmented setting [4], which evaluates a domain-specialized agent on Beer Game performance. SCM-Arena differs in scope and intent:

rather than evaluating a specific system, it provides a model-agnostic benchmark for characterizing behavioral profiles across frontier and open-weight LLMs under systematically varied conditions. The emphasis is on behavioral stability, degradation under constraint, and failure mode identification across a broad model population.

8 Limitations

SCM-Arena v1 is a stylized environment and does not capture the full complexity of real supply chains. The simulation models a single product with no pricing, capacity constraints, or contractual relationships. Tiers do not communicate beyond demand signal propagation. Prompt framing affects ordering behavior in ways that are condition-specific and not fully disentangled from model capability. Complexity scores are relative to the current benchmark population and will shift as models are added in future versions.

A structural limitation of any fixed-parameterization benchmark is susceptibility to passive strategies. As the gemma2:2b case demonstrates, a near-constant ordering policy can achieve low cost ratios in game modes where the optimal order quantity happens to coincide with a model’s default output. SCM-Arena partially addresses this through the modern game mode variant and the behavioral descriptors, but aggregate cost ratios should be read alongside complexity scores and condition sensitivity profiles rather than treated as a standalone ranking. These are intentional scoping decisions for v1 and are candidates for extension in subsequent releases.

9 Future Directions

SCM-Arena v1 covers one classic supply chain problem, ordering under delayed feedback, and several extensions follow naturally. The newsvendor problem is a candidate: a single-period inventory decision under demand uncertainty with a closed-form optimal solution, where the evaluation question shifts from coordination failure to cost-asymmetry reasoning. Multi-echelon replenishment and supplier selection under disruption present further environments where behavioral profiles generated by the same methodology could yield cross-problem comparisons not possible within a single testbed. The agent configuration could also be extended. V1 treats each tier independently, but future work could examine heterogeneous configurations where different models control different tiers, or competitive settings where LLMs negotiate directly against one another. Outcomes in those settings are relative rather than absolute, which makes evaluation harder, but they reflect how LLMs are increasingly deployed in practice. Finally, the versioned-release structure of v1 suggests a path toward longitudinal evaluation, tracking whether and how LLM decision behavior in operational tasks changes as model generations turn over.

10 Conclusion

SCM-Arena evaluates how LLMs make ordering decisions in a dynamic supply chain. The benchmark’s value is in the behavioral profiles it generates: which models degrade gracefully and which don’t. Aggregated results across 53,000 episodes, frozen and versioned, are accessible at scm-arena.com alongside the comparison platform.

Suggested Citation

Hasija, A., & Castillo, V.E. (2026). SCM-Arena v1: A Behavioral Benchmark for LLM Decision Policies in Supply Chains. *SSRN preprint*. Zenodo DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.19401615.

References

- [1] Sterman, J.D. (1989). Modeling managerial behavior: Misperceptions of feedback in a dynamic decision making experiment. *Management Science*, 35(3), 321–339.
- [2] Croson, R., & Donohue, K. (2006). Behavioral causes of the bullwhip effect and the observed value of inventory information. *Management Science*, 52(3), 323–336.
- [3] Li, S., et al. (2023). Large language models for supply chain optimization. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2307.03875*.
- [4] Zeng, Y., et al. (2025). LLMs for supply chain management. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2505.18597*.